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A valid neotype designation for *Vipera illyrica* LAURENTI, 1768

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KRECSÁK et al. (2024) demonstrated that the nomen *Vipera ammodytes ammodytes* (LINNAEUS, 1758) is associated with a type specimen from the restricted type locality of *Coluber ammodytes* to Belgrad village, Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality, Turkey (Türkiye). As a consequence, *Vipera illyrica* LAURENTI, 1768 becomes the oldest available nomen for the Nose-horned Vipers occurring in the northwestern portions of the species' distribution (the population previously considered to represent the nominotypical subspecies). KRECSÁK et al. (2025) reviewed the history of this taxon and made the case for the designation of a neotype in order to stabilize the usage of the species group name *illyrica*. They neglected to include an appropriate ZooBank pre-registration for their work in order to provide availability of their nomenclatural act, therefore the act would become available only following the publication of the printed edition of 'Salamandra' in 2026 (DUBOIS & FRÉTEY 2025, DENZER et al. 2025). We here provide again the neotype designation including a respective registration to provide a valid nomenclatural act.

The electronic edition of this article conforms to the requirements of the amended International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN 1999, 2012), and hence the nomenclatural act contained herein is available under that Code from the electronic edition of this article. This published work and the nomenclatural act it contains have been registered in ZooBank, the online registration system for the ICZN. The LSID (Life Science Identifier) for this publication is: urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:FBCDEEA1-7AB1-4572-B90F-2720F3991414. The electronic edition of this work was published in a journal with an ISSN, and has

been archived and is available from the following digital repositories: www.salamandra-journal.com, www.zenodo.org.

In order to stabilize the usage of the nomen *illyrica* as used for the Nose-horned Viper populations from Italy, Austria, Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, northern Albania, most of Serbia, and northwestern Bulgaria, and to stabilize its type locality, we here designate the adult male specimen NHMW 25274:6 in the Natural History Museum Vienna, collected in Trieste (45°39'01" N, 13°46'13" E), Friuli Venezia Giulia autonomous region, northeastern Italy, as the neotype for *Vipera illyrica* LAURENTI, 1768 in compliance with the Articles 72.2 and 75 of the Code (ICZN 1999). A full justification of this action was provided in KRECSÁK et al. (2025), but we here provide the minimum supporting information to satisfy Article 75.3 of the Code (ICZN 1999). The characters differentiating *Vipera illyrica* (currently treated as a taxon of subspecific rank: *Vipera ammodytes illyrica*) from other taxa are provided in KRECSÁK et al. (2025). The neotype has a snout–vent length of 526 mm, a tail length 68 mm, 153 ventral scales, 34/34 subcaudal scales, and 22 dorsal midbody scale rows. The colour in preservative is greyish-brown, with a black zig-zag pattern, venter black or bluish grey with white flecks.

As elaborated in KRECSÁK et al. (2025) and verified by numerous previous authors, no vipers, and thus none of the syntypes of *V. illyrica*, from the Museum Turrianum, used by J. N. LAURENTI himself, nor from the collection of U. ALDROVANDI, cited by LAURENTI (1768) in his description of *V. illyrica*, are known to be extant.

The neotype was collected in the immediate vicinity of the one precise locality “circa Castel de Duino” provided by LAURENTI (1768) and is fully consistent with the terse description of LAURENTI (1768). In a Discriminant Canonical Analysis the neotype falls within the 95% confidence interval of *V. a. illyrica* in a region of morphospace not overlapping with any other recognized subspecies of *V. ammodytes* (KRECSÁK et al. 2025).

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